

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC BASES OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: *Psycholinguistics has included a number of theories that give an explanation how a person can acquire a language, produce and perceive spoken and written language. The theories have been utilized in the language teaching field. Some language experts use them as the basic theories in developing the methods of language teaching. It is widely known as a psycholinguistics approach. The psycholinguistic method considers learning as an individual cognitive process which occurs within the individual and shifts to the social dimension. There are different strategies, such as natural method, whole physical response methods, and suggested contemporary method, which are founded on the theory of the psycholinguist. These methods use psychological concepts, like learning your first or second language (second language learning), learning a language (linguistic perception), and language (second language learning). The perception of languages refers to hearing and reading, while the creation of languages refers to speaking and writing.*

Key words: *psycholinguistics, creative activity, theory, approach, cognitive process, social dimension, natural method, total physical response method, suggestopedia method, linguistic perception.*

Psycholinguistics is the integration of two broad fields that are psychology and linguistics. Linguistics is the study of language, whereas psychology studies the mind and behavior. Therefore, psycholinguistics can generally be characterised as the study of mind and language. The correlation between the human mind and language is concerned when it makes analysis the procedures in the brain during producing language and perception.

Psycholinguistics includes three basic areas; language production, language perception and language acquisition. Language production means the processes involved in creating and expressing meaning through language, while language perception refers to processes involved in translating and comprehending written and spoken language. Language acquisition refers to processes of acquiring a native or a second language. That is why, In language teaching psycholinguistics as a study of the psychology of language is the most significant aspect. Because, it helps to study the psychological factors that are

possibly involved in language learning. Psycholinguistics mainly focuses on the application of the real language and interaction. It is crucial to make a decision in applying various methods that allow students to develop their creative activities by easily understand and use the language.

As an approach, there are some methods which were developed based on psycholinguistics theories and the methods have been widely utilized in the field of language teaching over the countries. Some kinds of the methods will be explained in this paper. To avoid misconception, some terms related to psycholinguistics and language learning and teaching will also explain in this paper.

Psycholinguistics Approach

Students are considered as people who always involve the three domains of psychology -cognitive, affective, and psychomotor- in their daily activities. The ability of using requires both receptive skill (listening and reading) and productive (speaking and writing) involving the three domains above. The forms of language are structured in human mind beings with interdependent connection of memory, perception, thought, meaning, and emotion (Demirezen, 2004). In acquiring language psycholinguistic approaches conceive language learning as a cognitive and individual process in which knowledge is organized as the learner is exposed to comprehensible input, is given opportunities to both, negotiate, and receive negative feedback. Psycholinguistic approaches to language learning tend to agree that a learner needs to be exposed to input (Carlos, 2008). One of the most widely investigated theories of input is Krashen's input hypothesis (1985). This theory predicts the likelihood for a learner to learn a language when seniors are exposed to comprehensible input. Thus, to increase the chances for input comprehension, input should be just one step beyond the learner's current stage of linguistic competence.

Relationship between psycholinguistics and creative activity

Psycholinguistics theories have explained the mental processes that occur in human brain during a person produces and perceives a language. Language perception includes the activity of listening and reading, while the language production includes the activity of speaking and writing that are considered as a creative activity. Following will be described some benefits of psycholinguistics theories in developing the creative activity of students.

Psycholinguistics Approach and Productive Skills

Psycholinguistics helps in understanding the students' mistakes in writing which aids them activate the creativity in the English language production. It has a clear contribution on spelling mistakes since in English words are not spelled as they sound. There is a difficulty on this case because storing of the spelling of words and retrieve them on demand is very hard. In addition, psycholinguistics approach shows that there are

mistakes in writing caused by agraphia, which must be treated properly. Psycholinguistics helps to find interesting topic to write that is very useful in acquiring the target language. It serves to decrease the level of the difficulties in writing. It helps to specify the writing levels and writing types. It pins down the mechanic mistakes on punctuation and suggests certain ways of avoiding them.

Moreover, psycholinguistic approach has a workable control over the field of teaching speaking as a skill. It has specified several difficulties on speaking such as students' oriented difficulty. Psycholinguistics also explains that personality, like introvert and extrovert students, affects students' performance in language learning. Speaking defects like voice disorders, stuttering, and disarticulation are also psychological in origin caused by personality factor. There are also some traumatic disorders such as aphasia and autism caused by localized in damage. It is recommend therapies and counseling practices for such difficulties. Thus, the investigations of psycholinguistic approach have provided solutions for almost each kind of language learning difficulty. With the knowledge, teachers can apply the appropriate techniques to teach speaking skills by considering the condition of the learner and find interesting topics to be discussed in speaking class.

Language Teaching Methods of Psycholinguistics Approach

An approach in language teaching includes theories of the language nature and the theories of language learning. Language teaching methods are concretization of language teaching approaches. A method of language teaching can be well understood if its fundamental theories are clearly understood. Followings are the major methods in developing student's language learning process:

Natural Method

The consistency of this method is shown by natural technique developed by teacher. Teacher activates the learners to competence activity such as problem solving, game, and humanistic affective. Problem solving is designed to train learners to find out a right situational answer or solution. Games are considered as an interlude activity, but it is designed to improve students' language competence. Humanistic affective is designed to implicate opinions, feelings, ideas, and reaction to language learning activity.

Total Physical Response Method

Related to kinesthetic theory, it is known that there is a positive relationship between physical movements and student's language achievement. It becomes the focus in designing and applying appropriate language teaching technique in a certain topic. A spacious classroom is required in applying this method. The class ideally consists of 20-25 students. This method can be applied to teach children or adults. Grammatical rules are presented in imperative sentences because basically all materials are presented in imperative sentences. In this method, dictionary is unneeded because the meaning of

words will be expressed by physical activities. Students usually do not get homework because language learning is performed together in the classroom.

Suggestopedia

Each meeting in this method is divided into three time allocations. The first is reviewing the previous topic through discussion, games, sketch, or role playing. If students do some mistakes, teacher corrects it carefully to keep a positive atmosphere. The second is distributing the dialogue traditionally. The third is relaxing students. This is divided into two: active activity and passive activity. Thus, it gives students an opportunity to use the language which means that they can be a good language user.

As a conclusion, by means of psycholinguistic approach, it is understood that we, as human beings, are innately and biologically programmed to acquire the first language, second and third languages, which may also be learned, if the right learning atmosphere furnished by the psycholinguistic approach is provided.

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